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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“ANG AKONG IRO”

Higala nakong taas ug balhibo,
ikog mag wagay-wagay kon siya lipay kaayo.

Linging kalimutaw
gakislap sa dakong gugma,
Bisan ug padlason, dili jud mupahawa.

Matag takna nga ikaw akong biyaan,
kay ako anaay obra ug mangitag kaayuhan.

Sa akong pag uli
ikaw mutagbo nga daw batang ga tibi,
Tingog mong gaparayig
abi nimo ug napiit.

Dagan, lukso, ug simhot sa akong kamot
Kalipay tika pinalangga kong iro.